

Sempers Ideenverknüpfung: Ideas, Acts, and Forms. Material Culture in Semper's Practical Aesthetics

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Abstract:

This essay reframes Gottfried Semper's practical aesthetics by placing the concept of "Ideenverknüpfung" (association of ideas) at the center of his theoretical project, arguing that British associationist psychology - absorbed during Semper's London exile (1850–1855) - provided the psychological mechanism that allowed Semper to link material acts, formal evolution, and symbolic meaning in a single coherent system. It is the psychological ligament for his theory of material transformation: *Stoffwechseltheorie*. This theory states that a structural motif survives thousands of years not just because craftsmen copy shapes, but because motifs migrate from one medium to another while preserving, through associative chains in the human mind, the symbolic memory of their technical and cultural origin.

Although essential for his theoretical framework, it has not been addressed by contemporary Scholarship.

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Introduction

Upon seeing the Great Exhibition of 1851, Gottfried Semper, a German architect and exile of the repressed 1848 revolution, was disturbed by the lack of expression and the poverty of ideas he witnessed in the examples of industrial production on display, a poverty caused by new industrial techniques.

The revolution of 1848 had been, after all, an uprising largely of impoverished journeymen whose work had been marginalized, while the Great Exhibition displayed precisely the machines that had displaced many of their trades. These events created a need not only to reconcile industrial progress with the expressive and cultural value of human labor, but also to understand the broader effects of technological change on human life.

In the following years, Semper published *Wissenschaft, Industrie und Kunst* (1852) and, later, *Der Stil* (1860–1863). In these works, he unfolds a theory of practical aesthetics that operates on three levels. It is practical because it focuses on the techniques, materials, and methods of making: how buildings and decorative arts are actually produced. It is anthropological because it treats these forms as expressions of human behavior and social organization, showing how art and craft reflect the cultural practices of a society. Finally, it is evolutionary because it traces the development of forms over time, arguing that architectural and decorative solutions adapt to technical, social, and material conditions, producing a historical logic in the evolution of style.

In addition to technological and social revolutions, Semper's theory was shaped by two important contemporary intellectual currents. The world was increasingly understood as governed by observable natural laws and progress described as the confluence of forces whose resultant defined historical development. A set of ideas sometimes simplified into positivism and provided a framework for interpreting cultural and artistic evolution. British Associationism, which modeled mental processes as linked chains of ideas, offered Semper a theory of mind to support his anthropological theory of formal evolution, connecting material change to the evolution of ideas.

I argue that it is the combination of these social experiences and philosophical influences that underlies Semper's conception of practical aesthetics, linking human labor, industrialization, and the evolution of form. Both the repressed revolution and the Great Exhibition, products of industrialization as well as of the cultural confrontations and intellectual exchanges of his years in exile, in Paris and especially London are essential for understanding and appreciating Semper's theory of practical aesthetics.

Part I: Biographical

Semper had studied architecture first in Munich, then in Paris.² In 1834, he was appointed at the Dresden Bauakademie, where he enjoyed a few productive years as a practicing architect. Semper was an active Republican and was active in several bourgeois-democratic associations. During the Dresden uprising of 1849, Semper worked on the construction of the barricades.³ After the revolution was ended with the help of Prussian troops, he found himself exiled.

After leaving Dresden he first spent a year in Paris. The city had become a safe haven for exiles and was now harbouring numerous German refugees. It was only in France that the revolution truly brought down the government and a short-lived Second Republic was installed. Paris was filled with the air of a revolutionary atmosphere and longing for a new social order. Marx had until recently been in Paris. Paris was also the city where Auguste Comte was theorizing about a *social physique*, the study of society as if it were a physical entity bound to the laws of nature, and in its extension a new secular vision for society. A society which should be scientifically organised. He called it *positivism*, an all encompassing philosophical system of encyclopedic proportions, which both explained and unified the sciences.

In Paris Semper was not able to make a living and in 1850, Semper moved to London. Here he spend five years. More importantly, in London, Semper found work. Henry Cole, civil servant, inventor and initiator of the Great Exhibition, had commissioned Semper to work on the exhibitions, most famously that of Canada, and here he got into contact with a wealth of different historical and cultural Styles.⁴ Semper also worked as director of the metal and woodworking division of the *Department of Practical Art* at *The School of Design*.⁵ Between 1853 and 1854, he also gave a series of lectures at the Marlborough House, or what was then the "National Art Training School". In these lectures he argued that art must be understood genealogically. By tracing its origins and evolution it would be possible to establish a true science of art that offers a comprehensive view of its domain and even form the basis for a doctrine of style.⁶

While Europe was swept with revolutions, Britain and its capital had stayed relatively peaceful. The Great Exhibition was in a sense a liberal and peaceful alternative to political upheaval. The purpose was to show that industrialisation and progress could go hand in hand, for the betterment of mankind. It was to harmonize art, science, and industry, to promote consumer taste, and to elevate

2 Magirius, "Gottfried Semper in Dresden," 480.

3 Quitzsch, *Gottfried Semper - Praktische Ästhetik und politischer Kampf*, 19.

4 Auerbach & Hoffenberg, *Britain, the Empire, and the World at the Great Exhibition of 1851*, 169.

5 Diephouse, "Science, Industry and Art: Gottfried Semper's Search for *Juste Milieu*," 16.

6 Mózo, "Introduction Gottfried Semper: Texts and Interpretations," in Hvattum, *Gottfried Semper and the Problem of Historicism*, 14.

the manufacturers' sense of aesthetics. It displayed technologies for mass-production and transport such as steam engines and locomotives, but also traditional works of craftsmanship, from all around the world. Besides showing the latest industrial inventions, it was displaying scientific developments. The event was conceived as an encyclopedia of things, presenting minerals, ancient sculpture, anthropological objects, and steam engines side by side. Objects that also offered an overview of the state of humanity and civilizations at different stages of development. The Great Exhibition seemed to be an empirical demonstration of the progress of civilization. The organizers even made fervent use of the first quantitative analyses of exhibition visitors. In this sense, the Great Exhibition became "an unofficial forum on the meanings of modernity."⁷

Positivism had not stayed isolated in Paris, but had crossed the Channel and was being discussed by thinkers such as John Stuart Mill and Herbert Spencer.⁸ Comte had posited that society could be understood as an accumulation of facts. Like Comte, they emphasized observation, logic, and in the case of Spencer the search for general laws.⁹ These thinkers shared an interest in the classification of knowledge and its interrelationships, an interest that – whatever the source - Semper shared.¹⁰ At the same time, associationism dominated British empiricism, and in extension, early psychology, and educational theory, but also theories of aesthetics. Associationist psychologists such as James Mill and Alexander Bain described the mind as a system of connections that attributes meaning to what is seen, heard, and done. Together, these currents offered a conceptual framework for understanding society as a complex, organized system. It are these intellectual currents that informs Semper's theory on the evolution of the practical arts.

To understand Semper's theories, it is crucial to situate them within this context of revolution, industrialization, the positivist view of progress and the associationist understanding of the mind. Like a revolutionary, he tried to define the artistic relationship between the arts and crafts; like a positivist, he saw society as a confluence of forces, within a singular equation: social, psychological, and symbolic; like an associationist, he viewed the minds as associative, where meaning is transposed from one form to another, generating a dynamic connection between the individual psyche and the social reality of a group. Semper integrated revolutionary, scientific, and psychological ideas into a unified approach to art, craft, and society.

After the Great Exhibition, Semper began publishing his most famous theoretical works. *Science, Industry, and Art* (*Wissenschaft, Industrie und Kunst*, 1852), was a review, but even more a critique of the exhibition, and the modernity it represented. During this time, he also produced preparatory

⁷ Shaers, *The great exhibition, 1851. A sourcebook*, 2

⁸ Lewisohn, Mill and Comte on the Methods of Social Science,

⁹ See, for instance, Herbert Spencer, "Progress: Its Law and Cause," in *Essays: Scientific and Speculative*, Vol. I, 26.

¹⁰ See Hvattum and Quitzsch

work for his later most important work, *Style in the Technical and Tectonic Arts, or Practical Aesthetics* (*Der Stil in den technischen und tektonischen Künsten oder Praktische Ästhetik*, 1860–1863), published in two volumes as a productive response to his own criticism, when Semper had already moved to Zürich where he had taken up teaching at the ETH.

It is the revolution of 1848 and his stay in London, the threads of Semper's life and interests have come together around the dominant themes of his time.

Part II: Sempers Criticism

“Where does the devaluation of matter through its treatment by machines, through substitutes for it, and through so many new inventions lead? Where does the devaluation of labor—whether in painting, sculpture, or other forms of artistic production, caused by the same factors—lead? I do not, of course, mean its devaluation in price, but in its significance, in its idea.”¹¹

In *Wissenschaft, Industrie und Kunst* (1852) Semper reflected on the cultural consequences of mechanization and the loss of material authenticity. Semper is impressed by industrial innovation, yet perplexed and convinced that the natural order of things has been reversed. In his view, markets now shape needs, rather than needs shaping markets - a development that threatens the cultural and symbolic value of materials, craft, and artistic labor. The book is besides an account of the event also a criticism on the capitalist mode of production, which was developing in tandem with a new industrialized society. It is almost as if a bit of Marx sounds through his words. But more importantly, at least for an architect, is that Semper sees the mechanic quality of industrial production to deprive architecture and craft, its formal expressivity, therefore its meaning.

What Semper witnesses at the World Exhibition is a loss of character and expressive articulations inherent to traditional production techniques. Mass produced objects all look the same and the direct relationship between craftsmen and art is lost. Character, Style and Expression, was not something, which this new logic of production, was able to replicate. Semper argues that markets push architects to produce in series and everything is – as he notes - adapted and cut-to-size for

11 Semper, *Wissenschaft, Industrie und Kunst*. 15. Original text: Wohin führt die Entwerthung der Materie durch ihre Behandlung mit der Maschine, durch Surrogate für sie und durch so viele neue Erfindungen? Wohin die Entwerthung der Arbeit, der malerischen, bildnerischen oder sonstigen Ausstattung, veranlasst durch die nämlichen Ursachen? Ich meine natürlich nicht ihre Entwerthung im Preise, sondern in der Bedeutung, in der Idee.

standardized products.¹² The Great Exhibition, which showcased the world, seemed to show the world to be finished. Semper claimed that there are no truly new artistic articulations and that it is needed to fully digest and decompose the existing formal tropes, before something new and good can enter the stage.¹³ It is here where Sempers project starts. As a program, which is to halt the degradation of meaning and which is to help digest the formal vocabulary of the past.

It is this cultural criticism from which Semper develops an anthropological theory of style, a doctrine of forms, ideas and ideals. Sempers project is an intellectual remedy against formal and ideal impoverishment brought forward by mechanisation, capitalism and a new kind of modernity.

Part III: The evolution of practice

In *Der Stil in den Technischen und Tektonischen Künsten oder Praktische Ästhetik* (1860–1863) Semper sets out to construct a comprehensive theory of style, which answers to his previous critique. A theory of style which consists both of a genealogy and a set of guidelines for what constitutes good style. His method is heterogeneous, incorporating historical examples, linguistic comparisons, and personal observations.

Sempers premise is that the evolution of style can be traced back to a set of original shapes, just as – in Sempers lifetime – historical linguistics had begun to shine a light on the common origin of the European language families. In his historical investigations Semper employs techniques that resemble those of etymology. He searches for and compares the lexicographic descriptions of particular techniques across different languages, tracing their semantic and material transformations over time, even if traces are dim, they convey something about their technical origin.¹⁴

Semper discusses Grundformen, Grundideen, and Urmotive, which emerge from the interaction between the human hand and materials, with or without tools, through actions such as kneading or hammering. These acts on matter give rise to shapes that form a vocabulary of forms. The earliest of these forms are the most clearly defined and purely articulated, while historical development proceeds from these primary forms toward progressively less articulated derivatives. Semper understood differences between architectural styles as the result of differences in material and

12 Semper, *Der Stil*, XVIII. An impoverishment he witnessed not only in industrial production, but also in new teaching at the Ecole de Polytechnique, which had adopted a kind of copy and paste strategy to design. Sempers thoughts were fuelled a polemic, not only against an industrial modernity, but extended against, what he called “Puristen, Schematiker und Zukünftler”.

13 Semper, *Wissenschaft, Industrie und Kunst*. 31.

14 Semper, *Der Stil. Erster Band: Textile Kunst*, 1.

geographical contexts that acted upon and interacted with the human physique and psyche. Consequently, his theory of style addressed both practical and symbolic aspects of form, with the latter emerging from the former.

For Semper, primitive artistic expressions thus illuminate the fundamental function of art as an essential condition of human society. For Semper, style is fundamentally about constructive articulation, expressed through actions such as kneading, binding, knotting, and weaving. Tectonics, he argues, are the visible result of these acts, and the plastic nature of a human-made artifact always conveys something of the process by which it was produced. In this way, both style and the ideas it embodies are inseparable from the acts performed on matter.

In his search for elementary forms and ideas, Semper traces back the practical arts to those techniques which he presumes to be the oldest: Pottery and Weaving. Especially the making of knots, he sees, as one of the oldest technologies. A technology which is both essential for clothing and early build structures. Semper speculates that from this elementary gesture unfolds a rich variety of derivative practices - knotting, weaving, binding - which, for him, constitute the fundamental vocabulary of the arts.

Semper makes recurrent use of the association of ideas: there is an “association between seam and knot”¹⁵ Upon seeing a weave or bread “the idea of binding is evoked through the association of ideas.”¹⁶ This is how forms gradually acquire semantic and mythological layers. Although this symbolism should be understood both in a utilitarian sense first and then in a symbolic or mythological sense. Motifs and ornament, even if they have lost their function, refer back to a physical use, to carry, to bind together, can express strength and fitnesses, even if a use has been lost, the original idea can still be expressed. This is essentially Sempers “Stoffwechseltheorie”: Stylistic elements are transposed from one material domain, for instance textile, or wood to another material domain, for instance stone. Even if the function disappears, the symbolic meaning remains. The ornament recalls the *idea* of its original use.

The knot and the weave also become expression for one of the earliest cosmogonical ideas.¹⁷ It is “the universally valid symbol of the primal interlinking of things”¹⁸ In this associative process, the act of binding becomes a symbol in its own right - the symbol of concatenation, which literally means the act of connecting things in a chain or sequence. It embodies a symbolic tradition found across cultures. As Sempers recalls that everywhere chains, knots, and interlaced threads can be found that both connect and separate, bind and differentiate. This decorative motif thus preserves

15 Semper, *Der Stil. Erster Band: Textile Kunst*, 73

16 Semper, *Der Stil. Erster Band: Textile Kunst*, 173

17 Semper, *Der Stil. Erster Band: Textile Kunst*, 169 Cosmogonic myths are narratives that describe the origins of the universe or cosmos.

18 Semper, *Der Stil. Erster Band: Textile Kunst*, 78

the memory of the act from which it originated. Its symbolic content derives directly from its original function. Ornament becomes, in this sense, a metaphor for ideation itself - a visible trace of the human impulse to link, to weave, and to generate meaning through the transformation of matter into form.

Semper's concern with the expressive and functional logic of ornament also extends to the creative process itself. The artist, in confronting the material and formal constraints of a work, is engaged in a process of ideation: a negotiation between inherited forms and technical possibilities. The artist continues an associative chain of reasoning that links material practice, form, and idea across time. In his own words:

“Even if we accept that these forms originally came from stonework, the sculptor would still have been guided by a line of ideas connecting what came before with what comes after, and shaped by the strict formal requirements of each structural element.”¹⁹

Ornament, for Semper, is a dynamic translation of the productive forces that were originally present in practical crafts and that evolved by imitating the laws of nature. What begins as a technical necessity - the joining, binding, or stitching together of materials - gradually acquires aesthetic autonomy. The practical techniques used to fasten pieces of cloth give rise to an aesthetic language that is later transferred to flat surfaces: first to textiles such as tapestries, carpets, and garments, and eventually to architectural ornament.

Part IV: Principles of Design

From his theoretical framework, Semper derives a set of rules and principles for design. Ornament, he insists, should not merely imitate nature, but should communicate technical functions and allow certain ideas to be inferred from form. Design should be suggestive. Thus, floral ornament is legitimate only insofar as it conveys something about the transference of force. The capital of a Corinthian column, for instance, should visibly express that it carries weight - that its leaves are

19 Semper, *Der Stil. Zweiter Band*, 222. Original Text: Wenn wir den technischen Ursprung dieser Formen aus dem Steinstil auch zugeben wollten, so würde der Bildhauer zu den Kunstformen seiner stehen gelassenen Dienste doch immer auf einem dem Vorhergeschickten und dem noch Folgenden ungefähr entsprechenden, an die absolut-formalen Bedingungen jedes tektonischen Gebildes anknüpfenden Ideengange geleitet worden sein.

under tension. The quality of design, for Semper, lies precisely in this coherence: that all structural elements work together to articulate material properties and the functions they perform.

Semper further elaborates this principle by warning against both naturalistic imitation and arbitrary artistic invention. The true task of ornament, he argues, is neither to reproduce appearances nor to indulge in capricious decoration, but to make the underlying technical process intelligible. Ornament must remain bound to its material and constructive origins, allowing the functional idea to manifest itself clearly through form.

Sempers tracery shows that a genealogy of method implies a genealogy of ideas, with a few elementary ideas emerging from rudimentary acts upon matter, and all other forms understood as combinatory derivatives. A design is eloquent, therefore, if its formal structure is capable of expressing these abstract concepts - concepts that originate in the most basic acts of movement, simple directional gestures such as up and down. Floral ornament in this sense is able “to express forces acting simultaneously or alternately in opposite directions.”²⁰

In a lecture at Marlborough House, Semper elaborated this symbolic dimension of ornament, noting that motifs borrowed from nature or early craft practices carry an inherent associative power. Also referring to their expressivity of fitness:

„The best expression of this can be found in certain types taken from nature as well as primitive industry, which, through an immediate association of ideas awake in us the physical sense or psychological consciousness that these linking, binding, and simultaneously framing parts that adorn the adornment, stand up to their functions in every relation.”²¹

Semper advocates for a modern understanding of ornament, which is not their for its own sake, but to communicate something physical. It should be related to the structural qualities and physics of building. Although he deduces his theories from history, Semper is not at all a historicist in the narrow sense, but a surprisingly modern thinker who foretells a functionalistic aesthetic.

20 Semper, *Der Stil. Erster Band: Textile Kunst*, 161.

21 Semper, “On the Formal Principles of Adornment and Its Meaning as a Symbol in Art,” 307.

Part IV: The Formula of Necessity

His anthropological theory culminates in what has been called a “formula of necessity.”²² This formula was a mathematical function, which included: social conditions, symbols, construction, style and a range of epistemological assertions. The formula $U = C(x,y,z,t,v,w \dots)$ displayed cultural evolution as the resultant of a confluence of forces, that influenced its direction. Semper's mathematical function bears an interesting resemblance to Spencer's "formula of evolution".

Spencer's Formula states that all phenomena, from the universe to societies, evolve from a simple, incoherent homogeneity to a complex, coherent heterogeneity. Spencer saw society and progress, similar to other natural phenomena, like a natural force, with a set of laws giving direction to its development. According to Herbert Spencer, “progress consists in a change from the homogeneous to the heterogeneous.”²³

Semper does something analogous. This is especially noticeable in Semper's speculative formula, which shows that he sees society as a lawful composition of different forces. He seeks a fundamental logic behind all styles. He argues that all architectural and artistic forms derive from elementary acts: weaving, knotting, binding, shaping, enclosing, covering. Acts which unfold historically into more complex symbolic and structural systems.²⁴

Semper's formula and his search of positive laws, his attempt to create a science of art, breath the air of positivism. In contemporary retrospectives, the Architectural Historian Mari Hvattum also observed with positivism went as far as saying that positivism was the “framework within which Semper's practical aesthetics was conceived.”²⁵ But, Comte did not allow psychology in his philosophical system, while in British intellectual culture of the mid nineteenth century, the interest in psychological phenomena and social progress went hand in hand.²⁶

22 Diephouse, “Science, Industry and Art: Gottfried Semper's Search for the *Juste Milieu*,” 26.

23 Spencer, *Essays: Scientific, & Speculative. Vol. I*, 10.

24 Shelton, “Spencer's Formula of Evolution,” 243.

25 Hvattum, *Gottfried Semper and the Problem of Historicism*, 142.

26 John Stuart Mill and Herbert Spencer attest to this synthesis between individual and society. The associative mind, for Semper as well, was one of a set of positive forces.

Part V: Associationism in der Stil

As we have seen, Gottfried Semper makes few, but consistent and very explicit references to the association of ideas in his two volumes of *Der Stil in den Technischen und Tektonischen Künsten oder Praktische Ästhetik* (1860–1863), particularly in the first part, where he traces the origins of the arts in the crafts. Occasionally he refers to it as “assoziation,” but more often he uses the German term “Ideenverküpfung.” Der Stil he repeatedly and explicitly mobilises the terms “Ideenverknüpfung,” “Ideenverbindung,” and – once – the direct loan-word “Ideenassociation” in passages that are structurally central. There is no conceptual introduction to the topic; Semper seems to assume a familiarity with the concept on the part of the reader. Consequently, his theory of association is present but not fully articulated.

Although Semper offers no systematic chapter on psychology, the concept of the association of ideas is not a peripheral metaphor the mechanism that holds his theory together. In the first volume of

Besides Semper’s own writing, probably exposure can be inferred from the intellectual context of his time and the importance associationism held in the nineteenth century. We will do this, not by going through the whole relevant literature, but by example.

It was fifteen years before Semper’s stay in London that John Loudon, the gardener and friend of Joseph Paxton - the landscape architect who designed the Crystal Palace - popularized Archibald Alison’s (1757–1839) ideas on taste in the magazine he published, *The Architectural Magazine*.

Beyond the magazine Alison experienced wide popularity in Victorian Britain. Not to say that Alison directly influenced Semper, but by example, he can show some of the thinking Semper saw himself confronted with.

For Alison associations mediate between memory and experience. They mediate between sound and emotions, between sounds and ideas, between sounds and place, between thought and circumstance. Associations designate the particular inscription into memory. It relates your opinion to the opinion of others. It is the source, which dictates the effect of a celebrated national song. It is fundamental to the way in which a certain theory can be beautiful, and he who contemplates „the genius of the painter, blends itself with the peculiar emotions which the picture itself can produce.“²⁷ Associations can induce the significance of an idea as much as it can enhance a thing. They are, as Alison states, expressive of a certain quality of mind. But perhaps the most beautiful preposition is the idea that emotions can be traced back to their origin:

27 Alison, *Essays on the Nature and Principles of Taste*, 26.

“Whatever the character of the original emotion may be, the subsequent images all seem to relate to this character; and if we trace them back, we shall discover not only a connection between the individual thoughts in the sequence, but also a general relation among the whole, along with a conformity to the peculiar emotion that first excited them.”²⁸

Alison’s proposition was not unique. The idea that one could trace associations was embedded in the logic of empiricism, and it underpinned much eighteenth- and nineteenth-century thought on aesthetics, pedagogy, and moral philosophy, providing a framework for understanding how sensory experiences give rise to ideas, feelings, and judgments. This notion is also present in historicist debates, in Alison’s theory of taste, and in John Stuart Mill’s utilitarianism. Alison proposed tracing associations as a means to understand one’s own aesthetic judgment. A contemporary of Semper, John Stuart Mill proposed tracing ideas as a way of understanding one’s moral judgment. For all three - Alison, Mill, and Semper – morality, meaning and taste could not be clearly separated.

Congruent with the intellectual currents of his time, Semper’s theory shares a similar logic. In his anthropological framework, however, the tracing of ideas extends across time, beyond recorded history: it compares cultures and follows ideas from object to action to formal expression, and back to the underlying concept. What makes his approach distinctive is his use of historical inferences, which aim not merely to explain singular associations, but to understand how they operate within broader historical and geographical contexts. With this method, Semper’s thinking was on par with the scientific reasoning of Spencer and, slightly later, Darwin - regardless of whether his specific theories proved correct.

Whether through direct reading or the saturated intellectual atmosphere of 1850s London, the result is the same: Semper integrates the British empiricist distinction of simple and complex ideas (mingled with a good dose of German aesthetic theory and Platonic motifs) and adapts it to an aesthetic grounded in practice: in doing rather than seeing.

His approach is therefore less semantic, emerging instead from the reciprocal relationship between observation and action. Whereas English empiricism often relied on metaphors in which ideas “furnish the mind” and observation is like reading letters on a page and single signs combine into complex compositions. Semper, on the other hand, equates the evolution of forms with the evolution of ideas. He uses the concept of association to suggest that the structural and constructive

28 Alison, *Essays on the Nature and Principles of Taste*, 55.

essence of architecture carries meaning, and that this meaning is embedded in the practical, material, and constructive history of form.

Semper traces the genesis of form not merely as stages of functional evolution, but as a symbiotic development between ideation and formal manipulation of matter. Meaning is derived from the material relations societies build over time. This is essential to the anthropological character of his theory: ideation is less visual than haptic and practical, emerging from acting upon matter. Binding and knotting are primary acts, performed on primary materials, representing primary ideas. At the same time, these acts serve as a metaphor for the traces of ideas themselves, which can be followed from more complex, diffuse, and synthetic alterations back to their sources.

Semper's innovation lies in the fact that, contrary to the empiricists, he began – as Mari Hvattum noted - to “relate what they think to what they do,” rather than to what they see.²⁹

Part VI: Conclusion

Material culture is - as Semper argued - dependent on both its objective and subjective counterparts. The concept of binding is associated with that of connecting. A knot, becoming a weave, transcends its original meaning, ultimately becoming reflective of the idea of creation itself. Therefore it is perhaps the knot that is most illustrative of Semper's thinking.

His work is filled with the traces of others. Semper's theory is a response both to his own experiences as an exiled revolutionary and to the impact of mechanization on the arts and crafts. It is equally shaped by an intellectual climate in which positivism and associationism attempted to understand mind and society.

As shown in his formula of evolution Herbert Spencer saw the evolution of society as developing from the simple to the complex. A concept awfully close to that of Semper, and which Semper equally cast in the shape of a mathematical formula. Within Semper's own formula, psychological considerations - especially the human urge to associate - play a constitutive, if often subversive, role. Unlike earlier associationist thinkers, he replaces *seeing* with *doing*; and unlike theorists who focused on singular or immediate associations, Semper situates these associations within historical and geographical contexts. These two notions - history as progressive and the mind as associative - form the basis for both a theory of formal development and a theory of symbolic expression. It is

²⁹ Hvattum, *Gottfried Semper and the Problem of Historicism*, 20.

what determines style. Semper establishes a methodological synthesis, similar to the positivist ideal of a unified science: one that uses comparative methods, historical tracery, and an implicit theory of mind, to link the practical act with the symbolic and the social.

In a sense, Semper's work is a meditation on how the body, the mind, and society meet in the act of making. Every knot, every woven thread, every shaping of clay or stone is simultaneously a practical solution, a symbolic gesture, and a record of thought. In his vision, culture, craft, and cognition are inseparable threads in a vast network of acts, associations, and meanings stretching across generations and geographies. Within this network, one can follow a knot - as Semper himself had done - from the earliest gestures of binding and weaving to the complex architecture of the nineteenth century. Semper's theory is, in essence, an attempt to map human experience itself through material forms and to analyse and understand traditional chains of association in order to digest them and make them productive for the future.

His work engages not only with the scientific and philosophical discourse of his time but also with the social and material challenges posed by industrialization and capitalism. Challenges that, in Semper's view, threatened to impoverish artistic expression. His critique of industrial modernity is, essentially, a critique of the breakdown of a traditional associative chain and its productive reimagination.

Part VII: The Historiographical Blind Spot

Semper does not explicitly declare himself an associationist, nor does he cite Bain or Mill, nor is it clear that Semper read Bain or Alison. Semper is not an associationist in the philosophical sense, but his genealogical method relies on the same mental mechanism that British associationism theorized: the linking of ideas. He uses the term "Ideenverknüpfung" repeatedly, he treats ornament as chains of thought, he describes meaning as transferred, linked, and accumulated, he explains symbolic functions through associative transformation, he interprets culture through genealogical linkage. This is associationist structure even if he does not name it. Therefore Semper's genealogical method depends on a theory of associative thinking that transforms British associationism into a material, practical, and cultural model of ideation.

Few has situated Semper in the larger 19th-century psychology of taste, even though Semper does exactly that. Mari Hvattum places Semper in "the context of nineteenth-century architectural,

philosophical, and scientific discourse.”³⁰ She refers back to previous interpretations, who construe Semper as an “idealist or a positivist”³¹ - which I agree with her – are probably both true. Quitzsch, like Hvattum, sees a familiarity with positivism³², but, in general, emphasizes industrialization and revolution as biographical sources of his thinking.

No one has systematically connected Semper to mid-century 19th British associationist psychology, even though he lived in London during the height of Bain, the Mills, and Spencer. He was in London in the same time as Ruskin, the prince of associationism and taste theorist Archibald Alison was still widely read. In the late 18th to mid 19th century, taste theory was filled with associationism. Improving taste being one of the goals of the Great Exhibition. Semper need not have read Bain or Alison systematically; rather, his London environment was already saturated with associationist thinking. This makes it highly plausible that Semper absorbed and transformed this framework into a genealogy of symbolic and constructive acts.

30 Hvattum, *Gottfried Semper and the Problem of Historicism*, 22.

31 Hvattum, *Gottfried Semper and the Problem of Historicism*, 22.

32 Quitzsch, *Gottfried Semper - Praktische Ästhetik und politischer Kampf*, 67.

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